

Effects of Dredging on Marine Mammals

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Abstract

The emphasis of this review was on the consequences of dredging operations on mammals inhabiting the marine environments. The present desktop study aims to add to the knowledge already provided by various researchers on the effects of dredging activities on marine mammalian species. The effects evaluated in this study are the direct and indirect. Among the direct effects are collision/vessel strikes, underwater noise and turbidity. The possibility of collision is there but minimal owing to the fact that dredgers are stationed in a place and when they move they do move it is at low speeds. The likely effects of noise from dredging activities range from short period avoidance, behavioural alterations plus acoustic masking emanating from hearing defect/damage. The indirect effects evaluated in this study are habitat degradation, marine organisms entrainment, contaminants remobilization, suspended sediments and sedimentation. These impacts biological resources that inhabit the sea bed (benthic communities). This is reflected on the marine mammals as there are obvious alterations in the prey species. Important habitats such as sea grass beds and spawning sites are mostly affected as they are either smothered, destroyed, buried or out rightly detached. Ingested contaminants cause disruptive effects on endocrine systems, reproductive process, lowering of the immune systems of individuals, and outbreak of diseases leading to higher number of deaths. Agitation of the seabed can bring about proteom increase in prey species (food) for the marine mammals, because of greater nutrient loads. However suspended sediment loads and sedimentation may affect their food by smothering invertebrates, eggs, and larvae. Creation of environmental windows is recommended to mitigate deleterious effects of dredging.

Keywords: Marine dredging, marine mammals, direct, and indirect effects.

INTRODUCTION

Dredging is the physical detachment or removal of aggregates (sand and gravels) from the floors or beds of rivers, estuaries, lakes, seas, oceans and other water bodies. It is an anthropogenic activity with environmental disturbance that has the capability to create and modify geomorphic units. Dredging has numerous uses and purposes and among these are: capital dredging for waterway or harbour development, land reclamation to mine aggregates from the sea floors for construction and for flood or erosion control, maintenance dredging to deepen or maintain navigable waterways or channels that are under siltation threat, harvesting materials dredging for substances like gold, diamonds or other valuable trace elements, fishing dredging for catching certain species of edible clams and crabs, preparatory (foundations) dredging work and for dykes, bridges, piers or docks or wharves purposes, environmental remediation, to reclaim areas affected by chemical spills, beach nourishment, peat extraction and anti-eutrophication etc (CEDA, 2011; Tillin et al., 2011; WODA., 2013; Chilaka., 2016). The emphasis of this review is on the consequences of dredging on marine mammals inhabiting the marine environments.

There are four dominant types of dredgers in use globally. These are the Trailing suction hopper dredgers (TSHD), Cutter-suction dredgers (CSD), Grab dredgers (GD), Backhoe/dipper dredgers (BHM). The TSHDs and CSDs are hydraulic in nature and are called suction dredgers while GDs and BHMs are mechanical dredgers. These dredgers are shown in figure 1. The type of dredger for use in any operation is a function of requirements, project demands and the nature of sea floor (Todd et al., 2014).

A trailing suction hopper dredger (TSHD) trails its suction pipe when in operation. The pipe is connected to a dredge drag head and loads the dredge spoil into the hopper(s) in the vessel. As the hoppers get filled, the TSHD moves to the disposal site and evacuates the material through doors in the hull or pumps it out of the hoppers. Most of the TSHD dredgers in Nigeria are imported from Europe and America and recently from China and are used for large scale reclamation projects such as the Eko Atlantic City in 2009/2010 and for operations at the Bonny River by Bonny Channel Company in 2008 (Chilaka., 2016, see Figure1). A cutter-suction dredgers (CSD) suction tube possesses a cutting device at the suction inlet. The device loosens the bed material and transfers it to the suction mouth. The dredged material with the use of a wear-resistant centrifugal pump is usually sucked up and discharged either via a pipe line or to a barge. Cutter-suction dredgers are commonly used in areas of hard geologies consisting of impermeable surface materials (such as gravelly deposits or exposed bedrock) where a standard suction dredger is less efficient.

(a).

(b).

Figure 1a, Dredger Types (a) TSHD (b) CSD (c) GRAB (d) BACKHOE (Source: Images of Dredgers, retrieved July 25, 2020 from <https://www.google.com.images of dredgers.>).

(c).

(d).

Figure 1b, Dredger Types (a) TSHD (b) CSD (c) GRAB (d) BACKHOE (Source: Images of Dredgers, retrieved July 25, 2020 from https://www.google.com/images_of_dredgers.)

Some cutter suction dredgers are produced in Nigeria by Nigerians for aggregates extractions for construction purposes. They can be employed in subsurface water blasting. A grab dredger picks up sea floor material with a clam shell bucket, that hangs from an onboard crane, crane barge, or a hydraulic arm, or mounted on a dragline. This technique is usually employed in bay mud excavation. Most of them are crane barges with spuds. The dredge can be positioned by lowering and raising of steel piles. A backhoe dredger has a backhoe like on some excavators. A usable crude backhoe dredger can be produced by mounting a land-type backhoe excavator on a pontoon featuring barge-mounted excavators. Small backhoe dredgers can be track-mounted and operate from the bank of ditches. It is equipped with a semi-open shell. The shell is filled moving towards the machine. Normally dredged material is loaded in barges. Backhoe dredger is mainly used in harbours and in shallow waters (EUDA, 2015).

Dredged materials (spoils) are vital resource for construction and other economic uses. In Nigeria, the mined aggregates (sands and gravels) are sine qua non as far as construction is concerned. Dredging activities are on fast increase in Nigeria and the products of dredging are on high demand. Two broad types of dredging activities in Nigeria are public and private sector dredging. Public sector dredging is carried out by the government for harbour/port development, inland waterways developments, and reclamation for road constructions. The private sector dredging are categorized into dredging activities carried out by Oil companies (for capital and maintenance dredging, Real estate companies(for housing estates developments) and dredging operators-for stockpiling of aggregates and onward sale for reclamation purposes (Wabote., 2007; Chilaka., 2016).

The need for dredged aggregates are exacerbated by housing needs due to increase in population. Many swamps and marshes are reclaimed for residential and commercial purposes in the coastal cities of Niger Delta region and in Lagos State, the commercial capital of Nigeria. Dredging services are required by the international oil companies in their swamp/marshy or land operations. Also sixty-five percent of all land and swamp operations by the Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) and probably other major oil companies need one form of dredging services or the other (Wabote., 2007). Estimates for sands needs/markets in Nigeria differ but industry sources are of the opinion that about 3 million cubic meter of sands would be needed from 2010 to 2020 (Chilaka., 2016).

Globally, aggregates are in very high demand. This is because of their uniqueness and indispensability in building and construction industries. According to Tillin et al., (2011), 20 million tons of

aggregates are dredged yearly in England and Wales waters. Also according to IDAC, (2012), the total turnover made by dredging contractors globally in 2012 was about €11370 which was greater than double of the year 2000 turnover. All these impact on the marine environments. Great number of the populace are flocking the coastal areas of the world to reside and make a living. This influx means that more houses for residential and industrial purposes need to be built to accommodate the teeming population and provide jobs for the people respectively. All these put demands on the exploitable marine aggregates which is essential for the provision of needed infrastructures.

It is a fact that dredging affects the marine ecosystem with deleterious impacts on the flora and fauna, proactive managements strategies should be put in place so that the living organisms are well protected and also that the habitats are not degraded. The effects of dredging and related activities on marine ecosystem (habitats, flora and fauna) have been discussed by numerous authors (such works by Thrush et al., 1995; Newell et al., 1998; ECI., 2009; Michel et al., 2013; Kjelland et al., 2015; Todd et al., 2015; O'Brien, 2016; Clement, 2017). Marine mammals play some vital roles in the aquatic ecosystem and have their unique importance to man and therefore should be preserved to avoid extinction. They need to be protected and preserved. Many of the marine mammals have gone extinct and a good number are endangered already. Their roles in the marine environments among others are maintenance of marine ecosystems by regulating the prey populations, and ocean nutrients recycling. Marine mammals are also hunted for food and other resources (e.g. the furs are highly valued). Marine mammals are very much in use in the military and in the tourism industry.

The objective of this study is to provide a desktop evaluation of the direct and indirect consequences of dredging to the marine mammals. Examples will given from the global waters which definitely reflect our local waters in Nigeria bearing in mind that the marine mammals exhibit similar characteristics. Technical papers, consultancy reports, published books and journals related to this present desktop study were reviewed. Some of the marine mammals sighted in the Nigerian waters are Humpback whales, Bottle nose dolphins, Pygmy dwarf whales, and Harbour dolphins.

Direct consequences

Physical wounds or outright deaths from collision/strikes, sound generation and enhanced turbidity are some of the effects of dredging on marine mammals.

Collision/Strikes

Marine mammals collision or crash with the dredger is a major cause of wounds or deaths among the marine mammals. Dredging vessels are not always stationary, they often move from the dredging sites to the evacuation/disposal sites, thus there is the possibility of collision with an escaping or migrating mammals. The risk of collision taking place between a dredge vessel and a marine mammal will be minimized if the operation is prohibited critical habitats and periods when the concerned species have distractions or have their young present (Todd et al., 2015). Best et al, (2001) reported that only one death incidence was recorded as a result of collision and that was the death of a southern right whale (*Eubalaena australis*). According to Clement (2017), the most reported cases of vessel strikes are that of mysticetes (baleen whales). Researches have shown that the possibility of strikes differs and this depends on vessel type, speed, location, species and behaviour (Van Waerebeek et al., 2007). A study of vessel strikes globally carried out by Laist et al., (2001) revealed that the whales usually struck by vessels were the right whales (*Eubalaena glacialis* and *E. australis*), fin whales (*Balaenoptera physalus*), humpback whales, sperm whales and gray whales (*Eschrichtius robustus*). Commercial vessels such as container ships can cause major injuries or death when they collide with marine mammals. The critically endangered North Atlantic right whale is particularly affected by vessel strikes (Conn & Silber, 2013). The Figure 3 below shows the remains of a North Atlantic right whale that collided with a ship propeller.

Figure 3. North Atlantic right whale remains after a collision with a ship propeller (Source: Conn & Silber, 2013)

According to Laist et al (2001) and Panigada et al. (2006) resting and feeding whales are prone to risks. They reported seasonal alterations in collision rates of fin whales with rates rising during months of intensive feeding. This is because feeding animals are distracted and less focused on vessel movements. All kinds and sizes of vessels have struck whales, the most grave collisions (fatal injury or deaths) took place with big (greater than 80 m) and swift moving ships (greater than 14kn or greater than 26km/hr; (Jensen & Silber, 2004). According to Jensen & Silber (2014), a southern right whale cow/calf pair was struck and killed by 110 m dredger in South Africa as it directly surfaced in front of it. With a careful managed dredging, prohibiting critical areas, and periods when animals might be distracted or zones of numerous calves, risks of strikes between marine mammals and active dredging vessels are minimized (Reilly, 1950).

Noise Effects

Noise pollution from anthropogenic activities such as dredging is another major concern for marine mammals. This is because below water surface noise pollution interferes with the abilities of certain marine mammals especially the cetaceans and pinniped to navigate, communicate, forage and locate both predators and prey (Todd et al., 2015). The likely effects of noise pollution from dredging and construction works range from short period avoidance, behavioural alterations plus acoustic masking emanating from hearing defect/damage(Kastak et al., 2005; Mooney et al., 2009; and Todd et al., 2015). According to Clark et al., (2009), the reproduction success of whales which subsequently affect populations can be impacted by sound masking. Energy expenditure can be affected and the duration of feeding or resting can be limited as a result of behavioural changes due to noise exposure (NRC, 2005). According to OSPAR (2009) and Todd et al., (2015), the sound levels from a dredger is generally lower than the one from big ocean going ship: 124 – 188 dB re 1 μ pa rms at 1 m versus 180 – 190 dB re 1 μ pa rms at 1 m, respectively. According to CEDA (2011) and WODA (2013), trailer suction hopper dredges (TSHD) and back-hoe dredges (BHD) generate low frequency omnidirectional sounds ranging from 100 to 500 Hz with their bandwidths fluctuating from 20Hz to 20 KHz. They found out that the ranges are function of aggregates extraction process, aggregates types, with coarse gravels producing greater sounds.

Noise from dredges can lead to stress in marine mammals and this can decrease their foraging effectiveness or enhance their vulnerability to diseases and toxins (Geraci & Lounsbry, 2001; Perrin et al., 2009). Southall et al., (2007) showed that information on the hearing range of the cetaceans is scanty but is believed that whales and dolphins hear over similar frequency ranges to the sounds they

generate although the hearing ranges can extend beyond that of frequencies used for vocalizations. Noise produced from dredging activities has the capabilities of affecting individuals and populations of marine mammals within the dredging vicinity at the time of the operations. According to Parks & Tyack, (2005); McCauley & Cato, 2003; Southall et al., (2007) the lower frequency vocalization ranges of southern right whales suggest that their best hearing abilities are at least between 50 Hz and 2 kHz, Humpbacks, 20 Hz to 12KHz, while the functional hearing of baleen whales is said to be between 7 Hz to 22 KHz respectively. According to Au et al., (2000) and Tervo et al., (2012), all marine mammals are prone to effects of dredge noise however the impacts might be very acute for baleen whales that communicate at a very low frequencies. Recent report has shown that minke whales (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) in Ireland coast exhibited avoidance behaviour from areas of high construction vessel traffic and dredge areas during gas pipeline installation (Anderwald et al., 2013). Pinnipeds are also affected by dredge noise because they employ sounds when looking for their mates and for communication (Van Opzeeland et al., 2010). According to Southall et al., (2007), Odontocetes (orca and dolphins) that normally communicate at greater frequency ranges than baleen whales have the capacity for echolocation (generation of biological sonar) for navigation and hunting, whereas dolphin's functional auditory range is believed to be quite big and can detect low frequency sounds with their sensitivity reducing at frequencies below 1 - 2 KHz. Biological masking of vital noises could reduce the possibilities of reproduction in pinnipeds if dredging takes place in breeding areas. According to Todd et al., (2015), the New Zealand fur seals (*Arctocephalus forsteri*) in Western Australia waters did not show any reaction due to disturbance as a result of dredging activities near the haul out sites. Noise resulting from cavitation of dredger propellers, dredger head vacuuming are found to mask the noise from other boats, thereby increasing the likelihood of ship strikes of West Indian manatees (*Trichechus manatus*) as a result of hearing behavioural effect (Gerstein et al., 2006). There is the possibility of protem auditory loss if the marine mammals are in the vicinity of the dredger for a long period but not auditory damage (Todd et al., (2015).

Turbidity

Turbidity is the indirect measure of the suspended sediment load. It expresses the optical properties in a sample and is a measure of the light rays being scattered and absorbed. The size, angularity, dissolved and suspended matter composition all determine the degree of scattering and absorption of light in water. According to Nightingale & Simenstad (2001), via the processes of reflection, refraction and absorption the suspended solids in the water scatters light wavelengths and decreases the light available to underwater environments. Turbidity measurements are usually reported in Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTUs) or alternatively in Jackson Turbidity Unit (JTU). Turbidity plumes are produced from sediments re-suspension at the dredge site and at any other site the where the dredge material is deposited (Clement, 2017). According to Hitchcock & Bell (2004), sediment plumes have the capacity to extend the effect of dredging to greater areas that would have been unaffected physically. High turbidity degrees and sediment plumes propagation generated by dredging and or dredge material disposal may have effect on immediate communities or those contiguous to the dredge sites (Sneddon et al., 2017). Study by Hitchcock & Bell (2004), has shown that the effects are usually short-lived and can last four to five tidal cycles maximum and are restricted to a few hundreds of meters from the disposal site (Newell et al., 1998). Nevertheless, marine mammals inhabit turbid environments globally. Many of the marine mammals make use of sophisticated sonar system to perceive the environs. There is no proof in the literature that turbidity affects cetaceans or sirenians and feeding techniques utilized by some mysticetes. Sediment plumes are created by grey whales and sirenians and this is an indication that individuals must have some degree of tolerance and are capable to feed in turbid environments (Todd et al., 2015). Impacts of turbidity on pinnipeds which off course do not produce sonar for detecting prey were explored by scholars and it was discovered that they did not have difficulty in hunting for prey and this proved that vision is not used to locate prey as increased turbidity did not pose a threat to them (Todd et al., 2015). Therefore vision is not necessary for the survival of the pinnipeds or their capacity to forage.

Indirect Effects

Dredging and disposal of dredge materials can lead to alterations to their physical environments, and their prey including release of toxins and pollutants from dredge spoil to the environment. According to Tillin et al., (2011), properties such as topography, water depth, particle size, suspended sediment

load, waves and tidal currents are changed by dredging. Changes can also take place as a result of natural events such as storm, runoff, tides, and waves. According to Todd et al., (2015) little changes are not likely to affect the marine ecosystem substantially and biodiversity increase, however large scale changes possess the potential to affect the whole food chain and the marine mammals. These effects can be either positive or negative and are species specific.

Negative/Adverse Effects

Some of these negative/adverse effects of dredging and dredge spoil disposal activities are, habitat degradation, marine organisms entrainment, marine contaminant pollution remobilization, suspended sediments and sedimentation.

Degradation of the habitat.

Habitat degradation is caused by a number of anthropogenic activities including dredging. Marine mammals that live in coastal environments are most likely to be affected by habitat degradation and loss. Habitat degradation also threatens marine mammals and their capacity to find and catch food. Dredging operations and spoil disposal have the ability to affect the food webs adversely (Clement, 2017). Important marine habitats such as sea grass beds and coral reefs are at very high risk to dredging activities. The major concerns are total eradication, smothering and reduction in light intensity (Erftemeijer et al., 2012). From the 45 case studies reviewed globally from 26 dredging projects in over five decades it was discovered that over 21, 023 ha of sea grass beds were lost (Erftemeijer & Lewis, 2006). This showed that habitats depletion or losses are enormous due to dredging operations. According to Marsh et al., (1982); Preen & Marsh, (1995); GBRMPA, (2011) as cited in Todd et al., 2015, some marine mammals like the sirenians are herbivorous animals and are wholly dependent on sea grass beds as source of food, so their eradication can have enormous consequences on the growth, survival, distribution and foraging habits. A broad class of sea grass has been seen in dugong stomach contents, and proof exists they will feed on algae if there is dearth of sea grass (Marsh, 1989; See figure 4).

Figure 4. A dugong feeding on the sea-floor (Source: Marsh, 1989)

According to Duarte, (2002); Orth et al., (2006), sea grass beds are vital parts of the marine ecosystem by virtue of their roles in primary production, nutrient cycling and stabilization of sediments. Sea grass beds offer great support to several coastal communities and give refuge for the coastal juvenile faunas and some marine mammals like the bottlenose dolphins which feed on preys within the sea grass beds (Shane, 1990; Heck et al., 2003).

From this, it is clear that alterations can adversely affect the food web at some levels and recovery will rely on species type, scope of depletion and destruction. Dredging operation can result to burial and smothering of the benthic species within the dredge sites and mostly at the spoil disposal areas. This can result to mortalities and shortage of food for the mammalian species. The effect of dredging on the sea grass can be short term and will not pose enough deleterious consequences on the marine mammals if the dredging operation is well planned. However, there will changes in prey species availability and their spatial distribution.

Marine organisms entrainment

All marine organisms are at a very high of risk of being removed by the suction field from the hydraulic dredgers. Nevertheless, presently there is no study on the effects of entrainment on the marine mammals though the effects on the prey species have been studied (Reine & Clarke, 1998; Nightingale & Simenstad, 2001). Benthic fauna and demersal fish that have strong association with bottom sediments are at greater risk to entrainment than the mobile species (Todd et al., 2015). Consequently the effect of this entrainment of benthic fauna is shortage of food (preys) for the marine mammals that depend on them for survival. Also dredging in the spawning areas can affect transition of organisms from young to adult which adversely influence structure and population. This is because the eggs and larvae are destroyed. Most bottom dwellers and mud burrowing species like clams, water snails and mollusks are destroyed and buried and these have negative effects on the food web. To guard against the adverse consequences of dredging on the eggs and larvae of the fish species protem restrictions (environmental windows) can be imposed on the dredging activities. This makes sure that activity is restricted in spawning and nursery grounds at critical periods. With respect to marine mammals, risk assessment need to be carried out prior to the dredging and if the activities are well managed decrease in prey population is not likely to be high to have adverse effects on the marine mammals' population.

Marine contaminant pollution

Dredging operations have the capability and potentials to release contaminants and toxic chemicals to the marine environments which can alter the chemical properties of the sediments and adversely affect the water quality. Contaminants and bacteria are easily adsorbed to marine sediments which can lead to their accumulation and bioturbation over time (Clement, 2017). Contaminants that are discharged into the marine environments accumulate in the bodies of marine mammals when they are stored in their blubbers along with energy unintentionally (Whitehead et al., 2000). Such contaminants found in the tissues of the marine mammals include heavy metals, such as mercury and lead, but also organo-chlorides and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Whitehead et al., 2000)). These can cause disruptive effects on endocrine systems, reproductive effects, lowering of the immune systems of individuals, and outbreak of diseases leading to a higher number of deaths (Vos et al., 2003). Dredging causes sediment re-suspension and makes the contaminants bio-available to the marine organisms through the food chain. This can pose considerable health risks to the marine mammals which can be derived directly from floating debris or indirectly through consumption of contaminants via exposed prey species (Clement, 2017). Contaminants remobilization and bioavailability is site specific, complicated and is determined by a number of factors like contaminant status, spoils chemical properties, contaminant uptake by the prey species, range and feeding habits of the local marine species (Todd et al., 2015; Clement, 2017). Remobilization of contaminants due to dredging is restricted spatio-temporally and as long as the contaminated sediments are properly managed, the concentrations will not be sufficient to have deleterious effects on the environments (Roberts, 2012). The risks will be high and with very great effects if contaminated sediments are dredged but with proper handling and disposal off the open ocean there will be minimal adverse impacts (Roberts, 2012).

Suspended sediments

Sediments are particles that have been generated, suspended, transported and deposited by water, and are natural and vital for elemental cycling in rivers, lakes and marine ecosystems (Beussink, 2007). According to Kjelland et al., (2015), suspended sediment events are important as nutrients and

contaminants fluxes that take place in coastal systems and oceans, rivers and other water bodies. The frequency and size of suspended sediment events can be changed by variables like land use changes and human activities including dredging operations. According to Charlton (2008), the suspended load consists of finer materials and usually includes clays, silts and sands. This material is carried aloft, suspended above the bed by turbulent eddies and is transported towards the direction of main water body flow. Increases in suspended sediments loads, frequencies and timing of events are usually related directly to anthropogenic activities such as vessels, navigation maintenance and construction, road and port construction, mining, agriculture, logging and urban development and indirectly through changed precipitation patterns temperature increase, and alterations in hard freezes, snow parks and snow melts associated to climate change (Kjelland et al., 2015). Dredging is a complex anthropogenic activity and its effects on aquatic ecosystems are poorly comprehended especially over long period of time. Turbidity has the potential to impact the feeding capacity of fish, however piscivorous fish that feed on larger prey which detect visually over longer distances are affected to a greater extent than planktivorous fish that detect prey visually over short distances (Utne-Palm, 2002; de Robertis et al., 2003). Changes in the choice of habitat, altered predator-prey relationships, and increased anti predator responses are other behavioral changes (see; Leahy et al., 2011; Wenger & McCormick, 2013; Wenger et al., 2013). High concentrations of suspended sediments can lead to gill damage in fish species (Wong et al., 2013). The effects of the suspended sediment concentrations on the invertebrates include abrasion, reduced rates of respirations due to filtration mechanisms clogging or behavioral changes. Foraging effectiveness of filter feeders can also be affected as a result of reduction in food-to-sediment ratio which cause more energy to be expended in sorting out additional material (Todd et al., 2015). Studies have shown that suspended sediments absorb heat energy and subsequently increase the water temperatures (Reid, 1961; Ryder & Pesendorfer, 1989). According to Berry et al., (2003), turbidity can reduce light transmission through the water and decrease photosynthesis by aquatic flora with consequent effects on the dissolved oxygen levels. The effects of turbidity on water quality may result to biological effects on aquatic organisms such as disruptions in migrations and spawning, movement patterns, sub lethal effects like susceptibility to disease, growth and development, reduced eggs hatching success, and direct deaths (Coen, 1995). Reactions to suspended sediment loads are species specific. Changes in behaviours noted in blue mussels (*Mytilus edulis*), queen scallops (*Aequipecten opercularis*), ross worms (*Sabellaria spinulosa*), and edible crabs (*Cancer pagurus*) exposed to suspended sediment concentrations of 12 and 71 mg l⁻¹ have the potential to impact physical fitness if the conditions are prolonged; nevertheless lethal effects were not noted for either concentrations (Last et al., 2011). Scholars like Morgan et al., 1983; Griffin et al., 2009; Suedel et al., 2012) addressed the impacts of suspended sediments on eggs and larvae of marine organisms under laboratory conditions. Some studies have suggested that suspended sediment concentrations have limited effects on egg hatching success. Conversely, Griffin et al., (2009) discovered that if the eggs of Pacific herring (*Clupea pallasii*) were exposed to suspended sediments of 250 and 500 mg l⁻¹ within 2 hours of dispersal, sediments that adhered to the outside of eggs will lead to increased egg-to-egg attachment, and abnormal larval development; ability to attach to surfaces could also be compromised. Sediment plumes can be modeled to predict the areas of highest concentrations, which imply that dredging activities can be well planned to avoid sensitive areas and periods such as spawning. Thus, lethal and long lasting effects on the marine organisms could be reduced, however short term effects are to be anticipated, significant impacts are unlikely on the marine mammals (Todd et al., 2015).

Sedimentation

According to Merriam-Webster's Dictionaries and Thesaurus, sedimentation is simply the action or process of forming or depositing sediment. Numerous studies are available on the effects of sedimentation or deposits on benthic macro invertebrate communities. These effects are important both as direct indicator of local aquatic health and as an indication of indirect effects to fish. The initial deleterious effects from dredging or dredge placement material (sedimentation) on benthic macro invertebrate communities include smothering, burial and initial depression of abundance and community structure with differences observed in recovery time and resultant community structure (Anchor Environmental, 2003; Berry et al., 2003; Cooper et al., 2007; Guerra et al., 2007; Wilbur et al., 2007, & Wilbur et al., 2008). The capacity to recover differs with species and depends on several factors such as sediment type, sedimentation depth, water depth, areal extent, and coastal

processes. In-filling of habitat interstices due to sedimentation injures crevice-inhabiting invertebrates and gravel-spawning fish species. According to Tillin et al., (2011), habitats made of fine grained sands with quick growing opportunistic species are less affected and have quicker recovery than stable coarse grained habitats with slow growing sessile flora and fauna. The sea bottom dwelling and immobile organisms and certain new born which are incapacitated to move from the dredgers' path are the worse hit.

However, the effects are species specific; also certain species can withstand burial and can burrow back to the surface. A study by Wiber et al., (2007), showed an initial decrease in the benthic macro invertebrate communities emanating from a burial depth of 2 to 10 cm and time of recovery ranging from 3 to 24 months compared to the reference site. Also it was reported that species composition and abundance were the same at ante and post disposal sites (Angonesi et al., 2006). According to Harvey et al., (1998) communities were seriously changed following the deposition of 1500 m³ of sediment and recovery of community structure similar to stable areas required over two years. Benthic macro invertebrate abundance and species composition were more at reference sites than at the dredged sites (Hayneys & Makarewicz, 1982). Bricelj et al., (1984) reported that hard shell clams have decreased growth rates at suspended sediment load above 40mg/L whereas the soft shell clams have damaged siphons, reduced oxygen consumption, feeding inhibition, and reduced responsiveness when exposed to 100 to 200 mg/L of suspended sediment (Grant & Thorpe, 1991).

As revealed by Last et al., (2011) through laboratory experiments, some species can survive prolonged burial periods in sediments(e.g. Ross worm), while others suffer high death rates if buried, some are able to come out from relatively thick sediments(e.g. Green sea urchin). According to Berry et al., (2011) eggs smothering through sedimentation can give rise to mass deaths, and delays in hatching. Also sediment deposition or placement can bring about a reduction in the number of settlement locations available to larvae that enhance competition level (Wilber et al., 2005). An attack on the wellbeing and health status of the benthic communities through sedimentation will definitely results to food deficiencies for the marine mammals at the higher trophic levels. Creation of environmental windows that eschews critical zones (e.g. spawning areas and nurseries) at the time of dredging operations is very essential and reduces large scale species depletions and important habitats.

Positive effects of Dredging

According to Newell et al., (2004); Claveleau & Desprez, (2009) in Todd et al., (2015), disturbance of sediments as a result of dredging has led to increase in species diversity and abundance of benthic fauna close to the dredge channels. The increment was attributed to organic nutrients release from the sediment plume (Oviatt et al., 1981; Walker & O' Donnell, 1981). This increases species abundance can definitely bring about protem availability of food to the marine mammals. Agitation of the seabed can bring about increased in prey species for the marine mammals, especially the bottom dwellers and mud burrowing organisms as they are removed from their natural habitats through dredging operations. Great numbers of bottle nose dolphins were seen clustered around Doonanierin Point in Ireland during construction activity, of which their presence may be as a result of enhanced number of the prey species among other factors (Anderwald et al., 2013).

The seabed is known to have an uneven topography and configuration with depressions and ridges of diverse sizes and shapes. Alterations in the seabed topography can positively influence the marine mammals. Some marine mammals may prefer foraging in previously dredged sites to un-dredged sites because of resident and visiting prey species in the areas. As cited in Todd et al., 2015, Ingle (1952) discovered that increment in food availability can lead to rise in the growth rates of marine organisms. He noted that oysters grew faster in high turbidity areas. At very high concentrations of suspended sediments ranging between 500 to 1000 mg l⁻¹ larval feeding rates of the Pacific herring increased tremendously over the control with 0 mg l⁻¹ of suspended sediments (Boehlert & Morgan, 1985). Increased turbidity plumes can also offer protection to some marine mammals against some visual carnivorous marine mammals like the killer whales and others that will find it difficult to hunt preys. Suspended sediments generations through dredging operations can go beyond the beneficial levels (threshold) and begin to have deleterious effects on the marine organisms.

CONCLUSION

In this desktop study, we reviewed the effects of one of the most important anthropogenic activities which have global significance. We looked at how it impacts marine mammals. Dredging is among the direct man – induced changes which has the potential to modify both fluvial and coastal ecosystems. At the onset of this study, we looked at dredger types and their mode of operations. The study highlighted the purposes and importance of dredging operations. We also enumerated the significance/roles of marine mammals in the coastal ecosystems and to humanity. The effects of dredging on marine mammals were classified into two groups. These are the direct and the indirect effects. Among the direct effects are collision/vessel strikes, sub water surface noise, and turbidity. There is every tendency of marine mammals colliding with the dredgers, but not probable going by the fact that dredgers are stationary or are moving at reduced speeds. Best et al, (2001) reported that only one death incidence was recorded as a result of collision and that was the death of a southern right whale (*Eubalaena australis*). The likely effects of noise pollution from dredging and construction works range from short period avoidance, behavioural alterations plus acoustic masking emanating from hearing defect/damage. Many of the marine mammals make use of sophisticated sonar system to perceive the environs. It has not been proved from literature that turbidity affects cetaceans or sirenians and feeding techniques utilized by some mysticetes.

Dredging operations can impact the marine mammals indirectly. Available habitats can be lost or degraded as a result of dredging activities. Important marine habitats such as sea grass beds and coral reefs are at very high risk to dredging activities. Habitat degradation also threatens marine mammals and their capacity to find and catch food. Entrainment affects benthic fauna, demersal fish, sea grass beds and spawning grounds that have strong association with bottom sediments than the mobile species. Consequently the effect of this is shortage of food (preys) for the marine mammals that depend on them for survival. Dredging operations have the capability and potentials to release contaminants and toxic chemicals to the marine environments. This can pose considerable health risks to the marine mammals which can be derived directly from floating debris or indirectly through consumption of contaminants via exposed prey species. Incremented Suspended sediment load and sedimentation can lead to in-filling of habitat interstices and injure crevice-occupying invertebrates and gravel-spawning fish species. Their effects on the invertebrates include abrasion, reduced rates of respirations due to filtration mechanisms clogging or behavioural changes.

Dredging can be beneficial or impact positively on the organisms as a result of increment in primary production and enrichment of nutrients from entrainment and sediments scattering. Incremented turbidity plumes can also offer protection to some marine mammals against some visual carnivorous sea mammals like the killer whales and others that will find it difficult to hunt preys.

Deleterious effects of dredging operations can be mitigated through the creation of environmental windows that is having some no go areas such as eschewing critical zones (e.g. spawning areas and nurseries) at the time of dredging operations is very essential and reduces large scale species depletions and will also reduce sedimentation due to dredging around oyster beds and other important habitats.

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